

FACTORS AFFECTING THE PREPARATION OF THE CHILD FOR SCHOOLING

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Annotation: Readiness for learning is the formation of all mental processes, as well as the personality of a preschooler as a whole, at the level that is necessary for successful adaptation and learning in elementary school. Despite the differences in approaches to learning, the parameters for which in currently assessing the readiness of the child for school. The prerequisites for successful schooling are the preparation of preschoolers for this.

Key words: upbringing, training, development, formation, socialization, preschool education, sources of preschool pedagogy, subject of preschool pedagogy, object of preschool pedagogy.

ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ПОДГОТОВКУ РЕБЕНКА К ШКОЛЬНОМУ ОБУЧЕНИЮ

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Аннотация: Готовностью к обучению – это сформированность всех психических процессов, а также личности дошкольника в целом на том уровне, который необходим для успешной адаптации и обучения в начальной школе. Несмотря на различия в подходах к обучению, по-прежнему остаются неизменными те параметры, по которым в настоящее время оценивают степень готовности ребенка к школе.

Ключевые слова: преобразование, обучение, развитие, формирование, социализация, дошкольное образование, источники дошкольной педагогики, предмет дошкольной педагогики, объект дошкольной педагогики.

If a child has reached the age of 5-7, this means that he has reached the finish line of education and upbringing in kindergarten. The senior and preparatory groups for school are a very important stage in the life of all children, because their further success in the first and subsequent grades depends on the correct preparation for the upcoming education in the initial link of the general education of the school.

What factors will affect the easy development of the school curriculum by the baby? Now, when there is one or two years left, how can you effectively prepare for primary school?

Some parents underestimate the importance of preschool in preparing a child for school, believing that everything that is needed will be taught in the first grade. But it is during this period that the foundation is laid for the excellent study of children in the first grade of the school, the motivation for learning, the desire to acquire and use new knowledge and skills are formed. If the skills necessary for learning are not formed, then the baby will most likely feel difficulties in mastering the first grade program, he will have a negative idea of the school, unwillingness to attend it. To avoid such negative consequences, it is very important to start now in a playful way, using different techniques, tasks, competitions and exercises to prepare the child for school.

Factors affecting the successful education of children in the primary level:

Good attention.

Excellent memory.

The ability to coherently build sentences and express their opinions.

Successful mastery of elementary mathematical concepts.

Knowledge of letters, correct pronunciation of sounds, ability to read syllables, small words.

Mastering social intelligence: the ability to communicate with friends and adults, non-conflict, knowledge of ethical standards, the ability to follow the rules of behavior in society.

Development of logical thinking.

Good motor skills of hands and fingers.

Broad outlook.

Physical development according to age.

Recommendations - How to develop the competencies necessary for school in a child of 5-7 years old:

The abundance of books in stores, information on the Internet can confuse parents. What is the best way to prepare your child for school? What methods are more efficient? Sometimes the abundance of information leads to the fact that the child is engaged for a very long time, because of this, he develops severe fatigue and, as a result, dislike for any type of activity. To avoid this, it is better to choose few tasks for your baby, but so that they efficiently and effectively solve the tasks. The main condition for the effectiveness of their implementation is not abundance, but regular use. Below are tasks, tips, exercises, games for developing the competencies necessary for the school.

Attention is very important for the correct and complete assimilation by the child of oral information, knowledge, instructions that the teacher will give at school. It is easy to train him in simple everyday, life situations and thanks to light games and exercises: ask the baby to fulfill your request with a complicated instruction (bring a green cup, which is in the sideboard on the lower shelf on the right), try not to repeat the instruction twice - the goal is for the child to fulfill the instruction is correct the first time, this task is a kind of test for the child's attentiveness; clap the rhythm, sing a short melody, say different syllable tracks - ask the baby to repeat after you;

graphic dictation by cells (the child, under the dictation of the parents, draws a hidden image, trying not to be distracted, so as not to confuse the drawing); among the many signs and symbols, find and cross out the named letter, number, geometric figure; find 10 differences in similar illustrations; draw the figure by cells, without errors, as in the sample; folding puzzles; for children already reading - find words on a sheet with mixed letters and mark;

in the rebus, find all the images and name, count them in a mixed picture.

Memory. Some guys manage to memorize a verse in 4-5 repetitions, and there are those who cannot cope with this task even after 3 weeks! This indicates a very low level of memory development. But it is precisely a good memory that will help your child out more than once when preparing school homework and when answering in class. Tasks for the development of memory are also very simple:

memorize with a child 1 - 2 poems a week from 3-4 quatrains, regularly repeating them on walks or when returning home from kindergarten;

the game "Memory" - you need to find a pair of pictures among the cards turned upside down: children gradually train to remember the location of more cards turned down; lay out 5 - 6 pictures in order, invite the baby to look for 5-10 seconds, and then mix and give the task to lay them out, as it was at the beginning;

read a fairy tale, story, invite the child to retell the content in his own words;

show a drawing of matches, counting sticks, invite the baby to lay it out from memory, without looking at the sample.

Connected speech. Without the ability to coherently express their thoughts, the child will experience great difficulty in answering at school, and may experience fear and discomfort because of this. A kid who easily expresses his thoughts is likely to use his speech just as skillfully when answering. If he experiences difficulties in constructing sentences, then, even knowing the answer, he will not be able to express it in words. Most often, excellent students are not those who know a lot, but those who clearly, skillfully and confidently speak. You can help your baby develop his speech right now thanks to easy exercises and tasks: invite the child to compose a story from a picture, from a series of interconnected illustrations, using complex sentences;

ask to tell about a trip to the village (a trip to a museum, a visit, etc.), which was a few days ago, to expand the ability to describe the details of the trip in words;

give the task to retell the cartoon or children's film in detail after watching;

constantly work on fixing the set sounds with the help of exercises recommended by a speech therapist, fixing their correct pronunciation in words and phrases.

Reading. Although there is no task in kindergarten to teach preschoolers to read, the basics of literacy are still given. Children memorize letters and learn to name them correctly and put them into syllables. But, as with memorizing verses and other information in the classroom, it is enough for some children to say a few times, show the letter - and they already know it well, and some, due to inattention or weak memory, cannot remember it for a long time, or remember, but it is often confused with other similar ones. If you want your child not to be behind in the classroom in reading, take extra lessons to familiarize yourself with letters, syllables and words at home.

Thus, caring parents, worrying that their baby is well prepared for learning in the first grade, from the age of 4 - 5 enroll him in preparatory courses for school, which develop classes. And some people successfully carry out this preparation at home - after all, mom and dad know the strengths and weaknesses of their baby better than all teachers and psychologists, they know well what should be worked hard and what abilities the crumbs should use along the way. Gradual preparation will help the child acquire the missing knowledge, skills and abilities and continue to study well in the primary school, perceiving learning not as a heavy duty, but as an exciting game in which he is certainly the winner.

Ильин, Е.П. Мотивация и мотивы [Текст]:учеб, пособие / Е.П. Ильин. – СПб.:ПИТЕР, 2000.-215с.

2). Larina V.P., Khodyreva E.A., Okunev A.A. Lectures at the creative laboratory "Modern pedagogical technologies" - Kirov: 1999 - 2002.

3). Petrusinsky V.V. Irgi - education, training, leisure. New school, 1994

four). Gromova O.K. "Critical thinking - how is it in Russian?" Creative technology. //BSh No. 12, 2001

4). Chawla, L. (2015). Benefits of nature contact for children. Journal of Planning Literature, 30(4), 433-452.

5). Louv, R. (2005). Last child in the woods: Saving our children from nature-deficit disorder. Algonquin Books.

6). Taylor, A. F., Kuo, F. E., & Sullivan, W. C. (2001). Coping with ADD: The surprising connection to green play settings. *Environment and Behavior*, 33(1), 54-77.

7). Wells, N. M., & Evans, G. W. (2003). Nearby nature: A buffer of life stress among

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